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Wireless Telemedicine Systems: An Overview

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Abstract- Rapid advances in information technology and telecommunications, and more specifically wireless and mobile communications, and their convergence (telematics) are leading to the emergence of a new type of information infrastructure that has the potential of supporting an array of advanced services for healthcare. The objective of this paper is to provide a snapshot of the applications of wireless telemedicine systems. A brief review of the spectrum of these applications and the potential benefits of these efforts will be presented, followed by success case studies in electronic patient record, emergency telemedicine, teleradiology, and home monitoring. It is anticipated that the progress carried out in these efforts, and the potential benefits of emerging mobile technologies will trigger the development of more applications, thus enabling the offering of a better service to the citizen.

Index Terms- Telemedicine, health systems, mobile, wireless, GSM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Telemedicine can be defined as the delivery of health care and sharing of medical knowledge over a distance using telecommunication means. It aims at providing expert based medical care to any place that health care is needed. Telemedicine as a concept was introduced about 30 years ago when telephone and fax machines were the first telecommunication means used. In recent years, several telemedicine applications have been successfully implemented over wired communication technologies like POTS, and ISDN. However, nowadays, modern wireless telecommunication means like the GSM and GPRS and the forthcoming UMTS mobile telephony standards, as well as satellite communications, allow the operation of wireless telemedicine systems freeing the medical personnel and/or the subject monitored bounded to fixed locations [1]-[3]. The objective of this paper is to present a review of wireless health systems.

Telemedicine applications, including those based on wireless technologies span the areas of emergency health care, telecardiology, teleradiology, telepathology, teledermatology, teleophthalmology, teleoncology, and telepsychiatry. In addition, health telematics applications enabling the availability of prompt and expert medical care have been exploited for the provision of health care services at understaffed areas like rural health centers, ambulance vehicles, ships, trains, airplanes as well as for home monitoring [4]- [10].

The structure of the paper is as follows. In section II, wireless technologies are introduced, followed by section III on transmission of digital images and video. In section IV, an overview of wireless telemedicine systems documented through published conference or journal papers is given, followed by a brief summary of completed and ongoing European Union (EU) funded projects in section V. Selected case studies of these systems are presented in section VI, followed by section VII on concluding remarks. A shorter version of this paper was published in [11].

TABLE I MAIN WIRELESS COMMUNICATION NETWORKS/STANDARDS

II. WIRELESS TECHNOLOGIES

In this section we briefly describe the main wireless technologies that have been used in wireless telemedicine systems, namely GSM, satellite, and wireless LAN (WLAN). These systems are summarized in Table I. GSM is a system currently in use, and is the second generation (2G) of the mobile communication networks. When it is in the standard mode of operation, it provides data transfer speeds of up to 9.6 kbps. Through the years a new technique was introduced in the GSM standard called High Speed Circuit Switched Data HSCSD. This technology makes it possible to use several time slots simultaneously when sending or receiving data, so the user can increase the data transmission to 14.4 kbps (an increase of 50%) or even triple at 43.3 kbps [12].

The evolution of mobile telecommunication systems from 2G to 2.5G (iDEN 64 kbps, GPRS 171 kbps, EDGE 384 kbps) and subsequently to 3G (W-CDMA, CDMA2000, TD-CDMA) systems will facilitate the provision of faster data transfer rates thus enabling the development of telemedicine systems that require high data transfer rates and are currently only feasible on wired communication networks [12].

Satellite systems are able to provide a variety data transfer rates starting from 2.4 kbps and moving to high-speed data rates of up to 2x64 kbps and even more. Satellite links also have the advantage of operating all over the world [13].

WLAN is a flexible data communications system implemented as an extension to or as an alternative for a wired LAN. Using radio frequency (RF) technology, WLANs transmit and receive data over the air, minimizing the need for wired connections. Thus, WLANs combine data connectivity with user mobility, becoming very popular in a number of vertical markets, including the healthcare, retail, manufacturing, warehousing, and academia. These industries have profited from the productivity gains of using hand-held terminals and notebook computers to transmit real-time information to centralized hosts for processing. Today wireless LANs are becoming more widely recognized as a general-purpose connectivity alternative for a broad range of applications, foreseeing that this technology will penetrate the health sector in the near future.

III. TRANSMISSION OF DIGITAL IMAGES AND VIDEO

A. Transmission of Digital Images

The use of digital imaging in medicine has benefited from the formation of the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) committee[14]. The committee was formed in 1983 by the American college of Radiology (ACR) and the National Equipment Manufacturers Association (NEMA). For still images, DICOM has adopted various JPEG variants such as: lossless JPEG, JPEG-LS [15], and it is expected to adopt JPEG 2000**Error! Reference source not found.** [16]. For digital video, the DICOM committee may adopt the MPEG-2 standard [17].

There are essentially no theoretical bandwidth requirements for transmitting medical images. In effect, lack of bandwidth can be compensated for by longer transmission times. Yet, high quality medical images such as a single chest radiograph may require from 40 to 50 Megabytes. In practice, it is desirable to at-least be able to transmit medical images during a single patient visit, so as to at-least avoid a follow-up visit.

Due to the diagnostic use of medical images, medical image compression techniques have primarily focused on lossless methods, where the image has to be reconstructed exactly from its compressed format [18]-[19]. Unfortunately, lossless methods can only provide limited compression ratios, usually ranging between 2 and 3.7 [20]. In lossy compression methods, the original image is only approximately reconstructed from its compressed format. Hence, adoption of lossy image compression

techniques requires the careful evaluation of the effect of compression on diagnostic performance [21]. In general, optimal performance requires the study of the impact of compression on different diagnostic situations. Clearly though, the background of most images are of no diagnostic value. Hence, Region of Interest (ROI) can be used to avoid compression of the background, and thus provide substantial improvements in compression ratios [22]. For example, if the region of interest covers about 20% of the entire image, average compression ratios of about 15.1 have been reported using JPEG-LS, while an average compression ratio of only 2.58 is possible for using the entire image as the region of interest [22].

Another solution is to provide a simple perceptual test where the participants are asked to identify the original image in a set that is composed of compressed images and the original image. Clearly, if the original image cannot be identified, then the compressed images that are confused as original will also not impact the diagnosis [22]. This technique leads to near lossless techniques where the uncompressed image differs from the original in only a small number of levels ($\pm 1, \pm 2$ out of a possible 4096 levels). For comparison, JPEG-LS in lossless mode provides for an average compression ratio of 2.58 that improves to 3.83 in the near-lossless mode (± 1 levels) [22]. In addition, for a region of interest that covers 20% of the image region, the average compression ratio improves from 15.1 to 22.0 [22].

B. Transmission of Digital Video

As mentioned earlier, the DICOM committee has not yet adopted any standard for digital video compression. The adoption of MPEG-2 is possible, but this is limited by the MPEG-2 requirement for constant delay method for frame synchronization [17],[23]. The constant delay requirement is not supported by ATM networks; making it difficult to deliver real-time MPEG-2 video over ATM [23]. On the other hand, the transmission of offline video is still possible.

It is important to distinguish among the requirements for: real-time video transmission, offline video transmission, medical video and audio for diagnostic applications, and non-diagnostic video and audio. Real-time video transmission for diagnostic applications is clearly the most demanding. Offline video transmission is essentially limited by the requirement to provide patient doctor interaction. Real-time diagnostic audio applications include the transmission of stethoscope audio, or the transmission of the audio stream that accompanies the diagnostic video. Good quality diagnostic audio at 38-128

kbps using Dolby AC-2 has been achieved, while MPEG-1 Layer 2 audio (32-256 kbps) or Dolby AC-3 (96-768 kbps) may also be used [23]. For non-diagnostic applications such as teleconferencing, H.261 (64 kbps - 1.92 Mbps) and H.263 (15-64 kbps) may be acceptable [23]. A typical application will require a diagnostic audio and video bitstream, in addition to a standard teleconferencing bitstream.

Due to the high bandwidth requirements and the frame synchronization problem, successful methods for real-time diagnostic video transmission will most likely require the adoption of the MPEG-4 standard [23]-[25]. The frame synchronization problem is alleviated in MPEG-4 via the use of timestamps on each frame [24]- [25]. A possible method for achieving acceptable video compression for diagnostic purposes may be possible through the use of object-based encoding and decoding. In object-based encoding and decoding, different bitrates are allocated to different parts of the digital video, according to the level of diagnostic importance. The advantage of this approach is that it can significantly reduce the required bandwidth while maintaining high-quality video images of the regions of diagnostic interest. As an example, it is important to note that most of the bandwidth in digital video transmission is spent on tracking moving objects in video images. Clearly, if there is no motion between successive images, then high-quality video can be achieved by simply encoding the small differences between video frames. This would be automatically detected in all video compression standards. Furthermore, in many clinical applications, such as in personal injury, it is clearly the case that the stationary part of the video is of significant importance, as opposed to moving objects in the background. A disadvantage of object based coding is that it is not always clear which part of the video is of diagnostic importance. This obstacle can be overcome by using interactive video, where the user can interactively select a region of interest.

IV. WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE SYSTEMS

The INSPEC and MEDLINE databases were searched with keywords: telemedicine and mobile, telemedicine and GSM, telemedicine and GPRS. The number of papers (including both conference and journal papers) published under these categories in the years 1979 to 2001 were 132. Out of these wireless telemedicine systems published in the literature, a total of 35 selected applications are briefly summarized in Table II . These systems covered a significant component of the whole spectrum of

health telematics applications, grouped in Table II primarily under the wireless technologies of GSM, satellite, radio, and wireless LAN. Under each of these technologies, the systems were grouped into the areas of emergency healthcare, telecardiology, teleradiology, telepsychology, teleophthalmology, and remote monitoring (including monitoring at rural health centers, home monitoring and subject monitoring at distant or isolated locations). In addition, in Table II, the data transmitted were coded under the following columns: signals for biosignals, IMG for medical imaging or video, EPR for electronic patient record, and AIV for audio (A) or image (I) or video (V) teleconferencing. The last column of Table II gives some comments characterizing the system described.

The majority of these applications (17) used the GSM network and were published between the years 1999 and 2001. These applications cover the areas of emergency telemedicine (7), remote monitoring (4) and telecardiology (3). Satellite links were also used in many telemedicine applications (12). Most of these systems were used for remote monitoring (8), followed by emergency telematics (2) and telecardiology (2). Satellite systems have the advantage of worldwide coverage and offer a variety of data transfer speeds, even though satellite links have the disadvantage of high operating cost. A few analog radio telemedicine systems were developed for the support of aircraft and ship in isolated areas. Finally, WLAN technology is an emerging technology already applied for emergency telematics and teleradiology.

TABLE II SELECTED APPLICATIONS OF WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE SYSTEMS

V. WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE EU FUNDED PROJECTS

The European Community has supported as well as is currently supporting wireless telemedicine projects under the following programs: (i) Third RTD Framework Programme 1990-1994, (ii) Fourth RTD Framework Programme 1994-1998, and (iii) Fifth RTD Framework Programme 1998-2002 [60].

Table III summarizes the projects funded under the 3rd and 4th framework programmes, whereas Table IV summarizes the ongoing projects under the 5th framework programme. Both tables are similarly structured. In Table III, the first column gives the project name/programme/duration/total cost and funding, the second column gives the area of application, whereas the third column gives the technology employed. The fourth column, data transmitted is structured similarly to Table II that is

subdivided under signals, images, electronic patient record, and teleconferencing mode. The last column gives the number of partners and countries involved.

Table III shows that most of the projects carried out under the two programmes in the time span 1990-1998 fall under the area of rural area support (6), followed by projects for emergency telematics (4). These projects exploited mainly the GSM and satellite wireless technologies. Most of the ongoing projects (1998-2002) fall under the areas of hospital support (3) and remote monitoring (3) (see Table IV). These projects exploit Bluetooth, UMTS, and GPRS wireless technologies.

TABLE III EU FUNDED WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE PROJECTS UNDER THE 3RD (1990-1994) AND 4TH (1994-1998) FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES

TABLE IV EU ONGOING WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE PROJECTS UNDER THE 5TH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME (1998-2002)

VI. CASE STUDIES

In this section, case studies of successful wireless telemedicine systems in emergency health telematics, telecardiology, teleradiology, electronic patient record and home monitoring are given.

A. Emergency Telemedicine: the Ambulance and Emergency-112 Projects [4]-[8]

The availability of prompt and expert medical care can meaningfully improve health care services at understaffed rural or remote areas. The provision of effective emergency telemedicine and home monitoring solutions are the major fields of interest of Ambulance HC1001 and Emergency-112 HC4027 projects that were partially funded by the European Commission / DGXIII TELEMATICS APPLICATION PROGRAMME. An overview of the concept of both projects is shown in Fig. 1.

The aim of the Ambulance [5] project was the development of a portable emergency telemedicine device that supports real-time transmission of critical biosignals as well as still images of the patient using the GSM link. This device can be used by paramedics or not specialized personnel that handle

emergency cases, in order to get directions from expert physicians. The system comprises of two different modules: (i) the mobile unit, which is located in an Ambulance vehicle near the patient, and (ii) the consultation unit, which is located at the hospital site and can be used by the experts in order to give directions. The system allows telediagnosis, long distance support and teleconsultation of mobile health care providers by experts located at an emergency coordination center or a specialized hospital.

Fig. 1. Overview of Ambulance and Emergency-112 projects.

EMERGENCY-112 [6]-[8], which was the extension of the Ambulance project, aimed the development of an integrated portable medical device for emergency telemedicine. The system enables the transmission of critical bio signals (ECG, BP, HR, SpO₂, temperature) and still images of the patient, from the emergency site to an emergency call center; thus enabling physicians to direct pre-hospital care in a more efficient way, improving patients outcome and reducing mortality. The system was designed in order to operate over several communication links such as Satellite, GSM, POTS and ISDN. In Emergency-112, emphasis was given on maximizing the system's future potential application, through the utilization of several communication links (both fixed and wireless), as well as through the increase of the overall system's usability, focusing on advanced user-interface and ergonomics. The system comprises of two different modules: (i) the patient unit which is the unit located near the patient (see Fig. 2). This unit can operate automatically over several communication means and has several operating features (depending on the case used) and (ii) the physician's unit which is the unit located near the expert doctor. This unit can operate over several communication links (depending on the place where the expert doctor is located).

Fig. 2. The portable version of Emergency-112 system.
(From Emergency-112 Project [9], © 2000 Emergency-112 HC4027, with permission)

Fig. 3. Emergency-112, network infrastructure for the island of Cyprus.

The final system was used in emergency health care provision over several communication links (ambulances, rural hospital centers or any other remotely located health center and navigating ships), and patient home monitoring. Emergency-112 has been used successfully since 1998 in three European Countries (Greece, Italy, Cyprus). The network infrastructure for the island of Cyprus is shown in Fig. 3.

B. Diagnostic accuracy of an ECG telecardiology service [61]

In this study the diagnostic accuracy of a telecardiology service in the daily activity of 150 general practitioners was evaluated. Each practitioner was equipped with a 12 lead ECG portable electrocardiograph (Card-Guard 7100) which was connected to a mobile (GSM) or fixed (POTS) connection. At the consultation site, a specialized cardiologist was available in order to give directions to the general practitioner. The system was tested for one year where 3456 calls took place. At the time of the ECG recording 44% of patients were symptomatic. ECG teleconsultation supported satisfactorily all the problems for 2452 patients (71%) whereas further diagnostic tests were requested in 862 patients (25%), and in 142 patients (4%) referral to the emergency department was given. Cardiological diagnosis was confirmed in 95 patients (73%), while anxiety or gastritis was presumed in 35 patients (27%). In the group of patients (n = 3314) for whom the cardiologist solved the problem without referral to the emergency department, there were 5 patients who were admitted to the emergency department for myocardial ischemia in the following 48 hours after the teleconsultation. The study concluded that the telecardiology service versus emergency department admission showed a sensitivity of 95%, a specificity of 97.5%, and a diagnostic accuracy of 92.5%.

C. A Teleradiology System Using a Mobile CT van and High Speed Satellite Communication [45]

In this system, a mobile van that houses a whole body spiral computed-tomography (CT) scanner and a second van that houses the satellite communications equipment was used for CT scanning, and on line two way transfer of image data and teleconferencing to a consultation center with various specialists. The personnel of the system consist of two drivers and a radiology technician who operates the CT scanner and the telecommunications unit. The mobile CT van is 12m long and is equipped with a whole body CT scanner, designed for lung disease screening. In addition, the van houses a PC for CT data transmission, teleconferencing equipment, image printer, facsimile machine, and resuscitation equipment. The stationery diagnostic center is equipped with a Sparc 1000, SUN Microsystems, Palo Alto, CA, server equipped with a disk array of 209GB, RAID 7, an image observer station with two units of 1728x2304, 21in monochrome monitor, and a 1280x1600 color monitor. The mobile and the stationary stations are communicating at 155 Mbps asynchronous transmission mode (ATM) via satellite or ISDN. The protocol used for image communication is DICOM 3.0 and for online diagnosis of CT screening of images it takes 10min. for the transmission of 16.5MB. The system was applied for the screening of 19117 residents of 29 districts in Japan that resulted in the identification of 75 cases of early lung cancer that were treated subsequently by partial

pneumonectomy. In addition, the system was applied to provide medical services in rural areas, sport events, and home monitoring. The usefulness of the proposed system is limited by the high initial cost for building the system (8.000.000 U.S. dollars), the number of subjects scanned, as well as by the satellite communications fee. These costs can be significantly lowered via the manufacture of 10 similar CT vans, doubling the number of subjects examined, and transmitting the images via the use of multiport format and in compressed format.

D. Electronic patient record: Mobile Medical Data (MOMEDA) [36],[55]-[57],[62]

The continuous and adequate information of patients about advanced medical procedures is a major factor for patient's overall satisfaction. Moreover, patients while hospitalized need to continue their daily routine or at least need to be able to communicate through modern means (via email or fax for example) with the outside world. On the other hand, specialized physicians that are moving inside or outside the hospital need to have complete and continuous information about patient's record in order to be able to provide the best medical practice. These are the main issues addressed by the Momedata HC4015 telemedicine project [62] that was partially funded from the European Commission / DGXIII TELEMATICS APPLICATION PROGRAMME. The system consisted of two modules as illustrated in Fig. 4: (i) the patient's information module, and (ii) the doctor's information module.

Fig. 4. Overview of Momedata project.

The main objective of the patient's information module was the development of a demonstrator called Personalized Medical System (PMIS) [55][56]. This system allows the access of customized disease-specific information from patients about their medical problem, the planned medical procedures, and what lifestyle they should have during hospitalization and afterwards.

Fig. 5. The doctor's hand held device as illustrated on the Momedata project web site.

(From Momedata webpage [62], © 1999 Momedata HC4015, with permission)

The main objective of the doctor's information module was the development of a demonstrator that allows the consulting physician to access electronic patient record using a hand held companion device connected to the GSM network [36][57]. A module based on the NOKIA communicator 9110 was developed (see Fig. 5) and tested through the project. The user of this module was able to connect to

the hospital main server and receive electronic record and medical images like MRI. The project was successfully tested in three European countries (Finland, Italy and Greece).

E. DITIS: Collaborative Virtual Medical Team for Home Healthcare of Cancer Patients [9]-[10]

Complex and chronic illnesses, such as cancer demand the use of specialized treatment protocols, administered and monitored by a coordinated team of professionals. Home based care of chronic illnesses (e.g. cancer patients) by a team of professionals is often a necessity, due to the protracted length of the illness, whereas hospital based treatment is limited, often demand based for short periods of time. As it is not possible for the health care team to be physically present by the patient at all times while the patient is undergoing treatment, a principal aim of the current project is to overcome this problem, through a network for medical collaboration DITIS (ΔΙΤΗΣ, in Greek, stands for: Network for Medical Collaboration) [9]-[10]. DITIS is a system that supports Virtual Medical Teams dealing with the home healthcare of cancer patients in Cyprus and is currently exploited at European level. It aims to support the creation, management and co-ordination of virtual medical teams, for the continuous treatment of the patient at home, and if needed, for periodic visits to places of specialized treatment and at home.

Fig. 6. DITIS network infrastructure for medical collaboration.

(From DITIS webpage [9], © 1999 DITIS project, with permission).

The design and development of DITIS telecooperation system (the infrastructure of which is given in Fig. 6) is based on internet and GSM/WAP connectivity, and includes the following five modules: (i) *Mobile agents* e.g. IBM's aglets workbench, Mitsubishi's Concordia, and Voyager, for the implementation of flexible communication infrastructure for the support of mobile users. The mobile agents may be extended to offer intelligence and co-operation. (ii) *Web based database* for the storage and processing of the *Electronic Medical Record*. (iii) *Telecooperation system* for sharing of information, team communication, coordination of team activities, and (iv) *Adaptive intelligent interface* for database access from a variety of access units, such as mobile computing units with GSM internet connectivity, and fixed units with internet access supporting telecooperation.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper attempted to give a snapshot of completed, ongoing and emerging applications of wireless information technology applications in health systems. Wireless telemedicine technology, linked with emerging technological trends like pervasive computing (enabling the seamless human-computer interactions with multimedia databases, “smart” cards), intelligent agent technology, electronic commerce applications in the healthcare sector, high-bandwidth Web, and citizen-centered services provide promising solutions for forthcoming healthcare applications [63]. These trends, together with, more work and efforts needed in the areas of interoperability, standards, security and legal issues [2] at both, national, and international levels will facilitate the wider application of healthcare telematics including wireless for the whole of the health care sector thus enabling the offering of a better service to the citizen. Concluding, some recommendations that will help the wider spread of wireless health systems are the following: (i) High-level political and managerial decision (including Government and private sector), commitment and leadership for the immediate promotion and application of wireless health systems in hospital operations and rural health centre services. (ii) Training of the physicians, the paramedical and administrative staff on the use and benefits of wireless information technology in medicine. (iii) Clarification of the legal and ethical issues.

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Fig. 1. Overview of Ambulance and Emergency-112 projects.

Fig. 2. The portable version of Emergency-112 system.
(From Emergency-112 Project [9], © 2000 Emergency-112 HC4027, with permission).

Fig. 3. Emergency-112, network infrastructure for the island of Cyprus.

Fig. 4. Overview of Mameda project.

MOMEDA Physician's terminal Demonstration

Fig. 5. The doctor's hand held device as shown on the Momedata project web site.

(From Momedata webpage [62], © 1999 Momedata HC4015, with permission).

Fig. 6. DITIS network infrastructure for medical collaboration.
 (From DITIS webpage [9], © 1999 DITIS project, with permission).

TABLE I. MAIN WIRELESS COMMUNICATION NETWORKS/STANDARDS

Type	Sub-type	Frequency band	Data transfer rates
GSM	GSM-900	900MHz	9.6 – 43.3 kbps
	GSM-1800	1800MHz	9.6 – 43.3 kbps
	GSM-1900	1900MHz	9.6 – 43.3 kbps
GPRS	GPRS	900/1800/1900 MHz	171.2 kbps
Wireless LAN	IEEE 802.11a	5GHz	20 Mbps
	IEEE 802.11b	2.4GHz	11 Mbps
	Hiperlan1	5GHz	20 Mbps
	Hiperlan2	5GHz	54 Mbps
	Bluetooth	2.4GHz	723.2 Mbps
Satellite	ICO	C, S band	2.4 kbps
	Globalstar	L, S, C band	7.2 kbps
	Iridium	L, Ka band	2.4 kbps
	Cyberstar	Ku, Ka band	400 kbps-30 Mbps
	Celestri	Ka band and 40-50 GHz	155 Mbps
	Teledesic	Ka band	16 kbps - 64 Mbps
	Skybridge	Ku band	16 kbps – 2 Mbps

TABLE II. SELECTED APPLICATIONS OF WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE SYSTEMS

Authors	Year	Area	Data Transmitted Signals ¹	IMG ² EPR ³ AIV ⁴	Comments
GSM					
Schöchinger <i>et al.</i>	[26]	99 Emergency			Early hospital admission
Karlstén <i>et al.</i>	[27]	00 Emergency	ECG		Ambulance triage support
Yan Xiao <i>et al.</i>	[28]	00 Emergency	BIO	V	Ambulance neurological examination support
Anantharaman <i>et al.</i>	[29]	01 Emergency	ECG		Pre-hospital support
Rodriguez <i>et al.</i>	[30]	01 Emergency	ECG		Cardiac arrest treatment
Istepanian <i>et al.</i>	[31][32]	01 Emergency	ECG		Wavelet ECG compression
Pavlopoulos <i>et al.</i>	[4][5]	01 Emergency	ECG, BP, Temp, SpO ₂ , CO ₂	A, I	Portable teleconsultation medical device
Reifart <i>et al.</i>	[33]	97 Telecardiology	ECG		12- lead ECG transmission
Istepanian <i>et al.</i>	[34]	99 Telecardiology	ECG, PPG		IS-54&GSM cellular telephone standards
Scalvini <i>et al.</i>	[35]	00 Telecardiology	ECG		Massive evaluation of an emergency ECG service
Reponen <i>et al.</i>	[36]	00 Teleradiology		CT	PDA based CT teleconsultation
Schulze <i>et al.</i>	[37]	00 Telepsychology			Support of patients with brain disturbances
Yogesán <i>et al.</i>	[38]	00 Teleophthalmology		ODI	Glaucoma screening
Hofman <i>et al.</i>	[39]	96 Remote monitoring	BIO		General purpose telemedicine system
Butera <i>et al.</i>	[40]	97 Remote monitoring			Support in disaster situations
Bukhers <i>et al.</i>	[41]	97 Remote monitoring		•	Real time patient-soldier battlefield monitoring
Woodward <i>et al.</i>	[42]	01 Remote monitoring	ECG		Mobile telephony ECG transmission
SATELLITE					
Murakami <i>et al.</i>	[43]	94 Emergency	ECG, BP	A, I	Telemedicine support in aircraft & ship
Kyriacou <i>et al.</i>	[4]	01 Emergency, Remote monitoring	ECG, BP	A, I	Portable teleconsultation medical device
Stewart <i>et al.</i>	[44]	99 Teleradiology		US, V	Ultra Sound image compression
Takizawa <i>et al.</i>	[45]	01 Teleradiology		CT	Spiral CT mobile van (lung cancer screening)
Yogesán <i>et al.</i>	[38]	00 Teleophthalmology		ODI	Glaucoma screening
Otto <i>et al.</i>	[46]	97 Remote monitoring	ECG, BP	V	Disaster situations
Anogianakis <i>et al.</i>	[47]	97 Remote monitoring		•	Maritime telemedicine
Samiotakis <i>et al.</i>	[48]	97 Remote monitoring		•	Basic telemedicine services
Navein <i>et al.</i>	[49]	98 Remote monitoring		V	US army portable telemedicine system
Lamminen <i>et al.</i>	[50]	99 Remote monitoring		A	Travellers and educators support
Pitsillides <i>et al.</i>	[10]	99 Remote monitoring		•, V	Monitoring of cancer patients
Harrett <i>et al.</i>	[51]	00 Remote monitoring			climbers' hypoxia monitoring
RADIO					
Schimizu <i>et al.</i>	[52]	99 Emergency	ECG, BP	V	Telemedicine support in aircraft & ship
Fuchs <i>et al.</i>	[53]	79 Remote monitoring		V	Telemedicine support in isolated areas
WLAN					
Banitsas <i>et al.</i>	[54]	Emergency		•, A, V	A&E ward mobile trolley
Reponen <i>et al.</i>	[57]	00 Teleradiology		CT, •	EPR data base teleconsultation
Finkelstein <i>et al.</i>	[58]	98 Remote monitoring	FVC		Home monitoring of asthma patients
Goussal <i>et al.</i>	[59]	97 Remote monitoring			Telemedicine support in isolated areas

¹Signals: ECG: Electrocardiograph, BIO: Biosignals, BP: Blood Pressure, Temp: Temperature, SpO₂: Oxygen saturation, CO₂: Carbon dioxide measurement, PPG: PhotoPlythiSmography, FVC: Forced Vital Capacity.

²IMG: Medical imaging, US: Ultrasound, CT: Computer Tomography, ODI: Optical Disc Image

³EPR: Electronic Patient Record

⁴AIV: Teleconferencing mode, A: Audio communication, I: Image communication (non medical), V: Video communication (non medical)

TABLE III EU FUNDED WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE PROJECTS UNDER THE
3RD (1990-1994) AND 4TH (1994-1998) FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES

Project / Programme / Duration/ total cost	Area	Comm. Technologies ¹	Data Transmitted				P/C ⁶
			Signals ²	IMG ³	EPR ⁴	AIV ⁵	
Multimedia portable digital assistant (MULTIPORT) / ACTS/ 1995-97(42 months) / 6.47 MECU	Hospital Rural areas	WLAN, GSM			•		7/4
Mobile Medical Data (MOMEDA)/ Telematics/ 98-00(24 m)/ 1.5 MECU	Hospital Rural areas	GSM		MRI XRay	•		11/3
Wireless atm network demonstrator (WAND) / ACTS/ 95-98 (36 m)/ 12.84 MECU	Rural areas	WATM				V	13/7
System for advanced <i>mobile</i> broadband applications (SAMBA) / ACTS/ 96-99(32m)/ 13.29 MECU	Rural areas	WATM				V	15/6
Mobile unit for health care provision via telematics support (AMBULANCE) / Telematics/ 96-97(24 m)/ 2.45 MECU	Emergency Rural areas	GSM	ECG, SPO2 BP, Temp			I	11/4
<i>Mobile</i> Experimental Broadband Interconnection Using Satellites (MOEBIUS) / Race 2 / 92-95(48 m)/	Emergency	SATH				V	12/6
European telemedicine for medical assistance (ET- ASSIST)/Telematics/ 96-99(36m)/ 3.85 MECU	Emergency	SAT, GSM			•		8/5
An Integrated Portable Device for Emergency Telemedicine (Emergency-112) / Telematics/ 98-00(24m)/ 0.9 MECU	Emergency Rural areas Remote monitoring	SAT, GSM	ECG, SPO2 BP, Temp			I	9/4

¹Communication Technologies: GSM: Global system for Mobile Communications, SAT: Satellite Communications, SATH: Satellite Communications (High speed data), WATM: Wireless ATM, WLAN: Wireless LAN

²Signals: ECG: Electrocardiograph, BIO: Biosignals, BP: Blood Pressure, Temp: Temperature, SpO2: Oxygen saturation, CO2: Carbon dioxide measurement.

³IMG: Medical imaging, MRI: Magnetic resonance image, XRay: XRay Images

⁴EPR: Electronic Patient Record

⁵AIV: Teleconferencing mode, A: Audio communication, I: Image communication (non medical), V: Video communication (non medical)

⁶P/C: Partners / Countries involved

TABLE IV EU ONGOING WIRELESS TELEMEDICINE PROJECTS UNDER THE 5TH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME (1998-2002)

Project / Programme / duration/ total cost, funding	Area	Comm. Technologies ¹	Data Transmitted			P/C ⁵
			Sign ²	Img ³	EPR ⁴	
Mobile devices for healthcare applications (MOBI-DEV) / IST/ 01-03(30m)/ 3.27 MECU, 1.75 MECU	Hospital	Bluetooth, UMTS			•	11/5
Continuous Care (C-CARE) / IST/ 00-02(26m)/ 2.69 MECU 1.36 MECU	Hospital	MCN			•	12/4
Mobile Workflow Support and InformAtion distribution in hospitals via voice-operateD, wIreless-Networked HANDheld PCs (WARD-IN-HAND) / IST/ 00-02(27m)/ 3.24 MECU, 1.7 MECU	Hospital	MCN			•	7/5
Personal intelligent health mobile systems for <i>Telecare</i> and Tele-consultation (HEALTHMATE) / IST/ 01-03(30m)/ 2.85 MECU, 1.43 MECU	Emergency Rural areas	GPRS UMTS			•	7/3
Mobile Tele-echography Using An Ultra-light Robot (OTELO) / IST/ 01-04(30)/ 3.34 MECU, 1.81 MECU	Tele- radiology	SAT GPRS		U/S		9/5
Enabling Best Practices For Oncology (BEPRO) / IST/ 01-02(18m)/ 1.47 MECU, 0.865 MECU	Tele – oncology	MCN			•	10/5
Distance Information Technologies For Home Care (CHS) / IST/ 00-02(36m)/ 2.87 MECU, 1.78 MECU	Remote monitoring	MCN		Diabetes ECG		9/6
Enhanced Personal, Intelligent and <i>Mobile</i> system for Early Detection and Interpretation of Cardiological Syndromes (EPI- MEDICS) / IST/ 01-03(36m)/ 2.44 MECU, 1.36 MECU	Remote monitoring	MCN		ECG		8/3
Telematic Support for Patient Focused Distant Care (TELEMEDICARE) / IST/ 00-02(30m)/ 3.65 MECU, 1.88 MECU	Remote monitoring	MCN		ECG BP SpO2 temp		7/4
Re-organising The Logistic, Delivery And Dosing Of Drugs (PHARMA) / IST/ 01-02(24m)/ 3.98 MECU, 2.03 MECU	Drugs delivery	MCN				8/4

¹ Communication Technologies: MCN: Mobile Communication Network

² Signals: ECG: Electrocardiogram, BP: Blood Pressure, Diabetes: Signals concerning diabetics monitoring (Glucose etc.).

³ IMG: Medical imaging, U/S: Ultrasound images

⁴ EPR: Electronic Patient Record

⁵ P/C: Partners / Countries involved